

Surface and subsurface compound marine heatwave and biogeochemical extremes under climate change

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Marine species are increasingly threatened by extreme and compound events, as warming, deoxygenation, and acidification unfold. Yet, the surface and especially the subsurface distribution and evolution of such compound events remain poorly understood. We present the current and projected distributions of compound marine heatwave (MHW), low oxygen (LOX), and high acidity (OAX) events throughout the water column, using observation-based data from 2004-2019 and large ensemble simulations from 1890-2100 based on an Earth system model. Our findings reveal that compound MHW-OAX and OAX-LOX events prevail in low to mid latitudes at the ocean surface. At 200m and 600m, MHW-OAX and MHW-LOX events are relatively frequent in high latitudes and parts of the tropics, while OAX-LOX events occur globally. Subsurface compound events are often associated with vertical displacements of water masses. Projections show a strong rise in compound event frequency primarily driven by shifts in mean oceanic conditions. The portion of the top 2000m affected by extreme or compound events rises from 20% to 98% under 2°C of global warming in a high emissions scenario using a preindustrial baseline, and to 30% using a shifting-mean baseline. This rise in surface and subsurface compound events poses a major threat to marine ecosystems.

Introduction

Ocean warming, acidification, and deoxygenation are key potential ecosystem stressors that challenge the sustainable management of living marine resources under climate change^{1,2,3}. On a global scale, the long-term evolution of these stressors are driven by human-induced CO₂ emissions and associated warming^{4,5,6}. The ocean

20 has taken up about 25% of the anthropogenic CO₂ emissions^{7,8,9} and most of the excess heat that has been generated by the changes in the Earth's radiative balance as a result of these emissions since 1960¹⁰. The uptake of CO₂ leads to ocean acidification^{11,12}, characterized by a rise in the hydrogen ion concentration [H⁺] and a corresponding decrease in pH = -log[H⁺]. Simultaneously, the uptake of excess energy causes ocean warming¹³. This warming together with the resulting changes in upper ocean stratification and circulation tend to reduce
25 the supply of dissolved oxygen (O₂) from the surface to the ocean's interior, causing ocean deoxygenation^{14,15,16}, and an expansion of low O₂ zones¹⁷.

The changes in ocean temperature, acidity and O₂ precondition the ocean for developing more extreme conditions in these stressors^{18,19,20}. Recent analyses confirm a rise in marine heatwaves (MHWs;^{18,19}), high acidity events (OAX;^{21,22,23}) and low oxygen extremes (LOX;^{24,25,26}) over the last few decades. An emerging
30 concern are compound events, i.e. situations where more than one of these potential ocean ecosystem stressors is outside the norm simultaneously or in close spatial proximity or temporal succession^{27,28}. Such compound events can occur when the drivers of one hazard simultaneously trigger additional hazards. For example, anomalous ocean heat uptake may drive not only heatwaves but also high [H⁺] events by elevating temperature²⁹, or low O₂ events in the thermocline by reducing O₂ solubility, increasing respiration rates, and limiting ocean
35 ventilation³⁰.

Compound events are of particularly high ecological concern, as their hazards can act synergistically^{31,32,33,34} and push marine ecosystems beyond the limits of adaptability. In fact, the most severe impacts on pelagic fish biomass seem to be driven by compound events³⁵. A well-known example is the 2013-2015 "Blob" in the northeastern Pacific, which refers to an extensive marine heatwave, when unusually high temperatures
40 co-occurred with low O₂, high [H⁺], and low net primary production^{36,37,38}. These multiple stressors had synergistic effects which amplified the heatwave's impacts on marine ecosystems^{37,38}. For example, low primary production reduced forage fish food supply, while high temperatures increased the metabolism and food demand of their predators, thereby depleting forage fish stocks and leading to die-offs of starving sea-birds³⁹. In addition, low O₂ combined with high [H⁺] may have lowered survival rates of fish and bivalves⁴⁰. Overall, this compound
45 extreme event had devastating impacts on local marine ecosystems and fisheries³⁶.

Despite the threat posed by compound extreme events to marine ecosystems, they remain relatively understudied, especially at depth due to limited data availability^{41,42,37,43,25}. Surface marine heatwaves have however been shown to extend into deeper waters, where they can persist long after dissipating at the surface^{44,30,45,46,47} and where they often co-occur with biogeochemical stressors such as low oxygen or high acidity^{48,49}. In addition,
50 the future evolution of compound extreme events under climate change remains poorly understood, with the exceptions of compound marine heatwave and high acidity events⁴² as well as compound marine heatwave and low oxygen events²⁵ at the surface. In recent years, however, global 3D monthly resolved observation-based datasets of biogeochemical ocean variables, such as oxygen and dissolved inorganic carbon, have been developed using

machine learning techniques applied to data from different monitoring campaigns. Some of these campaigns
55 deploy autonomous sensors, such as biogeochemical Argo floats, which sample the ocean throughout the upper
2000m of the ocean. In addition, new Earth system modelling approaches are facilitating the study of extreme
and compound extreme events in the ocean. Large ensemble simulations from Earth system models^{50,51,43} are
particularly valuable, as they provide the large datasets required for statistically robust analyses of these rare
events^{52,43,42,53}.

60 In this study, we leverage newly available global observation-based datasets of temperature, dissolved inor-
ganic carbon and oxygen^{54,55}, along with daily-mean output from large ensemble simulations⁴² of the Earth
system model GFDL-ESM2M^{56,57}, to analyse compound events involving marine heatwaves (MHWs), high
acidity (OAX), and low oxygen (LOX) conditions throughout the water column down to 2000m (Methods). We
start by characterizing the present-day frequency of these events and discussing their potential drivers. Then,
65 we assess the projected historical and future evolution of compound extreme events in the GFDL-ESM2M large
ensemble simulation (GFDL-ESM2M-LE), shedding light on the drivers of changes using various definitions of
extreme events⁴² (Methods).

Results

Present-day distribution

70 Between 2004 and 2019, the GFDL-ESM2M-LE simulates distinct frequency patterns of compound extreme
events defined at daily resolution using the 2004-2019 climatological baseline (Fig. 1). At the sea surface,
compound MHW-OAX events are most frequent in the subtropics, occurring more than 7 days per year, i.e.
more than twice the frequency expected if MHW and OAX events were independent ($LMF > 2$, Fig. 1a). In
contrast, these events are rare in the central and eastern equatorial Pacific, occurring less than half the expected
75 rate (< 1.82 day/year, $LMF < 0.5$, Fig. 1a). This pattern aligns with findings by Burger et al. 2022⁴², who found
higher MHW-OAX event frequency in regions where the positive effect on $[H^+]$ from increased temperatures
during MHWs outweighs the negative effect on $[H^+]$ from co-occurring decreases in dissolved inorganic carbon
(DIC). Surface compound MHW-LOX events are frequent globally (> 14.6 days per year, $LMF > 4$, Fig. 1b), since
MHWs are associated with decreased O_2 solubility. The pattern for surface OAX-LOX events mirrors that of
80 surface MHW-OAX due to spatially consistent negative correlation between T and O_2 (Fig. 1a,c). Therefore,
surface OAX-LOX events are also frequent in the subtropics and rare in the central and eastern equatorial
Pacific (Fig. 1c).

At subsurface, compound event likelihood patterns are relatively consistent below 1000m but vary notably
between 100m and 1000m (Fig. S1). To illustrate these differences, we focus on depth slices at 205m and
85 617m (model levels). These depths were chosen to capture key variations within the mesopelagic zone, a critical

Figure 1: **Present-day distribution of compound extreme oceanic events in the GFDL-ESM2M large ensemble simulation.** Ensemble mean likelihood multiplication factor (LMF) and associated frequency (days/year) of (a,d,g) compound marine heatwave (MHW) and high acidity (OAX) events, (b,e,h) compound marine heatwave (MHW) and low oxygen (LOX) events, and (c,f,i) compound OAX and LOX events at the (a-c) sea surface, (d-f) 205m, and (g-i) 617m depth, over 2004-2019. An LMF of unity indicates that compound events occur as frequently as expected if univariate extreme events were independent. An LMF of more than 1 (e.g, 2) means compound events occur more often (respectively, twice) as expected. Areas with no compound events over 2004-2019 (LMF=0) are in black. For comparison with observations and CMIP6 models, the zonal mean Pearson correlation coefficient between anomalies of monthly-mean temperature (T) and hydrogen ion concentration ($[H^+]$), of T and dissolved oxygen concentration (O_2), and of $[H^+]$ and O_2 relative to the seasonal cycle is shown on the right of the maps in black for the GFDL-ESM2M-LE, in a black dotted line for observations, and in orange for the mean of multiple CMIP6 models. Note that we compare correlations at 200m and 600m instead of 205m and 617m to match the vertical levels of the observations and CMIP6 data. The black and orange shadings indicate ± 1 standard deviation across the GFDL-ESM2M-LE and across CMIP6 models, respectively.

habitat for many marine organisms⁵⁸. At 205m and 617m, MHW-OAX events are rare across most of the low to mid latitudes (<1.82 day/year, $LMF < 0.5$, Fig. 1d,g), with some regions, such as the Pacific subtropical gyres, showing no occurrences. However, MHW-OAX events are frequent at higher latitudes (>11 days/year, $LMF > 3$, Fig. 1d,g) and at 617m in the South Atlantic and parts of the Indian Ocean (Fig. 1g). Similarly, MHW-LOX events are rare at 205m in the low to mid latitudes and at 617m in the North Pacific and in parts of the Indian and southern Pacific Ocean (<1.82 day/year, $LMF < 0.25$, Fig. 1e,h). Certain areas, such as the North Pacific subtropical gyre, also show almost no occurrences. However, MHW-LOX events are relatively frequent in high latitude regions at both 205m and 617m (often >14.6 days/year, $LMF > 4$, Fig. 1e,h), and at 617m in tropical regions. Compound OAX-LOX events are common across most of the global ocean at both 205m and 617m (>11 days/year, $LMF > 3$, Fig. 1f,i), except for part of the eastern equatorial Pacific at 617m, where they are almost non-existent.

The distribution of compound extreme events (Fig. 1) reflects the correlation between T, $[H^+]$ and O_2 (Methods, Fig. S2). High MHW-OAX event frequency occurs where T and $[H^+]$ anomalies, relative to the seasonal cycle, are positively correlated, high MHW-LOX event frequency occurs where T and O_2 anomalies are negatively correlated, and high OAX-LOX event frequency occurs where $[H^+]$ and O_2 anomalies are negatively correlated.

To assess the model's ability to capture these patterns, we use newly available monthly-resolved global observation-based datasets of T, DIC and O_2 (see Methods). Direct comparison of compound event frequencies between the GFDL-ESM2M-LE and observations is not possible due to the short observation period, which is insufficient for robust analysis of rare events in observations. Instead, we compare the correlation between T, $[H^+]$, and O_2 monthly-mean anomalies. Overall, the zonal mean correlation is similar in sign when calculated from the GFDL-ESM2M-LE and from observations (black and black dotted lines in Fig. 1). However, the model shows higher correlation between T and $[H^+]$ and between $[H^+]$ and O_2 in the low to mid latitudes at 205m and 617m, and between T and O_2 at surface compared to the observation-based estimates. Nevertheless, the observation-based products are uncertain, especially at subsurface and at local scale, and $[H^+]$ is reconstructed from sparse DIC observations using two successive algorithms (see "Observation-based data" in the Methods). Compared to CMIP6 models (orange envelope on Fig. 1), the GFDL-ESM2M shows notably similar correlation patterns. As CMIP6 model often lack daily-mean subsurface data and do not include multiple ensemble members, the GFDL-ESM2M is well suited for analyzing rare compound events at subsurface, despite some uncertainties in representing MHW-OAX and OAX-LOX events at subsurface levels.

Potential drivers of subsurface compound events

Subsurface compound extreme events can be driven by various physical processes⁴⁷. Shallow events confined in the mixed layer can be driven by anomalous air-sea heat fluxes, ocean advection or reduced wind-induced

Figure 2: Link between climatological mean vertical gradients of temperature, H^+ concentration, and oxygen concentration, the mean density anomaly during compound events, and compound event likelihood at 617m in the GFDL-ESM2M-LE. Ensemble mean vertical gradient of (a) temperature ($\delta_z T$), (b) $[\text{H}^+]$ ($\delta_z \text{H}^+$) and (c) oxygen ($\delta_z \text{O}_2$) concentration over 2004-2019. Ensemble mean anomaly of the potential density referenced to 0 dbar relative to its seasonal cycle, during (d) compound marine heatwave (MHW) and high acidity (OAX) events, (e) compound marine heatwave (MHW) and low oxygen (LOX) events, and (f) compound OAX-LOX events over 2004-2019. (g) Link between $\delta_z T$ and $\delta_z \text{H}^+$ and the likelihood of compound marine heatwave and high acidity (MHW-OAX) events. (h) Link between $\delta_z T$ and $\delta_z \text{O}_2$ and the likelihood of compound marine heatwave and low oxygen (MHW-LOX) events. (i) Link between $\delta_z \text{H}^+$ and $\delta_z \text{O}_2$ and the likelihood of compound high acidity and low oxygen (OAX-LOX) events. Favorable gradients, in red, correspond to regions where (g) T and $[\text{H}^+]$ vary in the same direction, (h) T and O_2 vary in opposite directions, and (i) $[\text{H}^+]$ and O_2 vary in opposite directions, in vice-versa for adverse gradients in blue. Darker colors indicate regions where favorable gradients are associated with frequent compound events (likelihood multiplication factor >1) and where adverse gradients are associated with rare compound events ($\text{LMF} < 1$), as expected when considering isopycnal displacements as principal compound event driver.

turbulent mixing. Below the mixed layer, potential drivers are eddies, current meanders, large-scale ocean
120 advection, and vertical displacements of the thermocline and water masses often due to anomalous surface
winds or the passage of large-scale planetary waves shifting isopycnals. Additionally, OAX and LOX events
can be driven by biological processes, including local sources and sinks of $[H^+]$ and O_2 from organic matter
production and remineralization. While our available model output does not allow us to quantify the individual
contribution of these processes to driving compound events, we assess whether compound events are associated
125 with vertical displacements of isopycnals, indicated by density anomalies.

Vertical displacements of isopycnals can explain frequent compound MHW-OAX events over regions where
T and $[H^+]$ vary in the same direction with depth, frequent MHW-LOX events over regions where climatological
mean T and O_2 vary in opposite directions, and frequent OAX-LOX events over regions where $[H^+]$ and O_2
vary in opposite directions. At 617 m (as well as at 205m, Fig. S3), these vertical gradient conditions are often
130 met (Fig. 2a-c). In the low to mid latitudes and in parts of the high latitudes, isopycnal deepening during
MHW-OAX events (Fig. 2d) brings warmer water downwards (Fig. 2a). This water contains lower $[H^+]$ in the
Pacific, but higher $[H^+]$ in the Atlantic where biological carbon is concentrated at shallower depths, as well as
in the high latitudes (Fig. 2b). As a result, compound MHW-OAX events are rare in the Pacific (in dark blue
in Fig. 2g) but frequent in the Atlantic and at high latitudes (in dark red in Fig. 2g). O_2 decreases with depth
135 in the mid latitudes of the Pacific and Indian Ocean (Fig. 2c), where deepening isopycnals (Fig. 2e) introduce
warmer T and higher O_2 , thus preventing MHW-LOX events (in dark blue Fig. 2h). Conversely, in the low to
mid latitudes of the Atlantic and in the equatorial Indian Ocean, where O_2 minima are shallower and O_2
increases with depth around 617m, a deepening of isopycnals is linked to more frequent MHW-LOX events. $[H^+]$
and O_2 vary in opposite directions over most of the global ocean (Fig. 2b,c), supporting frequent compound
140 OAX-LOX (in dark red in Fig. 2i).

While most regions with favorable vertical gradients align with areas of frequent compound events (in dark
red, Fig. 2g-i), not all regions with adverse vertical gradients correspond to regions of rare compound events (in
dark blue, Fig. 2g-i). For example, compound MHW-LOX events occur relatively often in the Southern Ocean,
despite adverse vertical gradients (in light blue in Fig. 2h). Overall, favorable and adverse vertical gradient
145 patterns align with compound event frequencies patterns (dark red or dark blue in Fig. 2g-i) in 76%, 60%, and
82% of the global ocean area for compound MHW-OAX, MHW-LOX, and OAX-LOX events, respectively, at
617m. At 205m, this alignment holds for 87%, 71%, and 93% of the ocean area (Fig. S3g-i).

The GFDL-ESM2M-LE captures vertical gradient patterns of T, $[H^+]$ and O_2 similar to those in observation-
based products, though there are local discrepancies, such as in the South Pacific for $[H^+]$ at 617m (Fig. S4).
150 The portion of the ocean area where both the GFDL-ESM2M-LE and observation-based products agree on the
sign of these gradients is 95%, 69%, and 57%, respectively, for T, $[H^+]$ and O_2 . This suggests that the model
may accurately represent patterns of compound event frequency over regions where they are driven by isopycnal

Figure 3: **Historical and future changes in compound event frequency in the GFDL-ESM2M large ensemble simulation.** Ensemble and global mean frequency (days/years) of compound marine heatwave and high acidity (MHW-OAX) events, compound marine heatwave and low oxygen (MHW-LOX) events, and compound high acidity and low oxygen (OAX-LOX) events from 1891 to 2100, at the surface (in blue), at 205m (in orange) and at 617m (in red) under a fixed preindustrial baseline (first row), a shifting-mean baseline (second row), and a fully-adapting baseline (third row). The frequency is indicated with identical y-scale on each row. The shading corresponds to ± 1 ensemble standard deviation, which indicates the spread in global mean frequency over the 15 ensemble members.

displacements. However, additional processes, such as remineralization which produces $[H^+]$ and consumes O_2 , may also drive compound events at subsurface levels. Further research is needed to quantify these contributions.

155 Historical and future changes

Under climate change, the frequency of compound MHW-OAX, MHW-LOX, and OAX-LOX events defined relative to a fixed preindustrial baseline is projected to strongly increase (Fig. 3a-c). These increases are most pronounced at the sea surface (Fig. 3a-c, in blue), where the frequencies of compound MHW-OAX, MHW-LOX, and OAX-LOX events have already increased by 150 days/year, 103 days/year, and 138 days/year, respectively, from 1891 to 2005. Under the high emissions - no mitigation RCP85 scenario, these frequencies are projected to rapidly increase through 2100, until reaching an almost constant compound event state where more than 80% of

days feature a compound MHW-OAX, MHW-LOX, and/or OAX-LOX event. This increase in compound event frequency coincides with an increase in individual MHW, OAX and LOX events at the surface (Fig. S5a-c, in blue). Notably, OAX events increased by 328 days/year between 1891 and 2005, leading to a nearly permanent
165 OAX state by 2005 in the GFDL-ESM2M-LE (Fig. S5b, in blue). Changes in LOX event frequency mirror MHW trends due to reduced solubility during MHWs, making post-2005 changes in compound MHW-OAX, MHW-LOX, and OAX-LOX event frequency largely driven by MHW changes.

At 2°C global warming (year 2050 in the GFDL-ESM2M-LE under the RCP8.5 scenario), surface compound event frequencies are projected to strongly increase compared to 1891-1900, especially in the low to mid latitudes
170 (Fig. 4a-c). Exceptions include the northern North Atlantic and parts of the Southern Ocean, where the frequency decreases by up to 40 days/year. In the North Atlantic, surface cooling (Fig. S6a) driven by the slowdown of the Atlantic Meridional Circulation⁵⁹ and rising oxygen levels contribute to the reduction in compound event frequency. Similarly, in the Southern Ocean, surface cooling linked to a wind-induced northward transport of sea-ice around Antarctica, which enhances surface stratification and hinders mixing
175 with the warmer waters below, contributes to decreasing compound event frequency⁶⁰.

The rise in surface compound events under a fixed preindustrial baseline is mainly driven by long-term trends in warming, acidification, and deoxygenation, as indicated by significantly reduced frequency increases under a shifting-mean baseline (Fig. 3d-f compared to a-c, in blue). The largest global increases under a shifting-mean baseline (up to 15 days/year) are projected for compound MHW-OAX and OAX-LOX events between 1891 and
180 2100 (Fig. 3d,f, in blue). Rising $[H^+]$ variability under higher DIC conditions in a future climate contributes to a higher frequency of OAX events (Fig. S5e, in blue;^{22,42}), thereby increasing the global mean frequency of MHW-OAX and OAX-LOX events (Fig. 3d,f). SST variability also increases in the high latitudes, where the seasonal cycle of T is gaining in amplitude⁶¹. The GFDL-ESM2M projects higher summer temperatures in the Arctic Ocean, thereby increasing the global mean frequency of MHWs (Fig. S7d), MHW-OAX and MHW-LOX
185 events (Fig. 3d,e). The increase in MHW-OAX, MHW-LOX and OAX-LOX events is particularly pronounced in the Arctic Ocean, where sea-ice melting allows for increased seasonality and air-driven surface ocean variability (Fig. 4d-f). Changes in the tail dependence between T, H^+ , and O_2 anomalies also contribute to frequency changes, which are revealed under a fully-adapting baseline. We find minor reductions in the frequency of surface MHW-OAX and OAX-LOX events, by 1 and 2 days/year respectively over 2000-2100 (Fig. 3j,l, in blue).
190 The decline in T- H^+ and H^+ - O_2 covariability may be attributed to the diminishing dominance of temperature effects on $[H^+]$ relative to the increasing impact of DIC on $[H^+]$ at higher DIC-concentration (Fig. S8a)^{42,62}.

Subsurface trends in compound event frequency generally mirror those at sea surface but are slightly weaker, as surface warming, deoxygenation, and acidification take time to propagate to deeper layers. Interestingly, changes at 617m under a fixed baseline (Fig. 3a,b,c, in pink) are somewhat stronger than those at 205m
195 (Fig. 3a,b,c, in yellow). Between 1891 and 2100, compound MHW-OAX, MHW-LOX, and OAX-LOX event

Figure 4: **Projected changes in surface compound event distribution between the preindustrial period and a 2°C warming level in the GFDL-ESM2M large ensemble simulation under RCP8.5.** Change in the frequency (days/year) of compound marine heatwave and high acidity (MHW-OAX) events, compound marine heatwave and low oxygen (MHW-LOX) events, and compound high acidity and low oxygen (OAX-LOX) events between 1891-1900 and a 11-year period centered around the year when the ensemble mean air surface temperature has reached $+2^{\circ}\text{C}$ compared to 1891-1900 in the RCP8.5 scenario, using a (first row) fixed, (second row) shifting-mean, and (third row) fully-adapting baseline. Note that the color scale differs between panels.

Figure 5: **Projected changes in subsurface compound event distribution at 617m between the preindustrial period and a 2°C warming level in the GFDL-ESM2M large ensemble simulation under RCP8.5.** Change in the frequency (days/year) of compound marine heatwave and high acidity (MHW-OAX) events, compound marine heatwave and low oxygen (MHW-LOX) events, and compound high acidity and low oxygen (OAX-LOX) events between 1891-1900 and a 11-year period centered around the year when the ensemble mean air surface temperature has reached $+2^{\circ}\text{C}$ compared to 1891-1900, using a (first row) fixed, (second row) shifting-mean, and (third row) fully-adapting baseline. Note that the color scale differs between panels.

frequency at 617m increase by 290 days/year, 140 days/year and 156 days/year, respectively, whereas at 205 m, these events increase by 274 days/year, 128 days/year and 160 days/year, respectively (Fig. 3a,b,c, in yellow). This is explained by narrower variability range of T, $[H^+]$, and O_2 values at depth, making shifts in their mean under climate change more likely to trigger extreme events.

200 Local changes in compound event frequency at 617m reflect the spatial pattern of changes in univariate event frequency (Fig. 5a-c against Fig. S9a-c), which are mainly driven by long-term mean changes in T, $[H^+]$, and O_2 . Warming is widespread across the global ocean, except in the mid-latitudes of the western Pacific (Fig. S6g), where increased stratification is projected to intensify the upper subtropical gyres⁶³, thereby shoaling isopycnals around 25°N and 25°S in the GFDL-ESM2M-LE (not shown). Acidification at this depth is absent
205 in the central equatorial Pacific (Fig. S6h). There, waters are too old to be influenced by anthropogenic carbon (more than 500 years) and water masses shift to younger, lighter water with lower DIC under 2°C warming compared to preindustrial conditions (Fig. S8b). Deoxygenation at high latitudes (Fig. S6i) is associated with reduced ventilation, whereas O_2 changes in the low latitudes remain highly model-dependent and thus uncertain^{15,16,64,6}. The GFDL-ESM2M-LE projects changes in H^+ - O_2 covariability at 617m resulting in a
210 10 days/year decrease in OAX-LOX event frequency over 2000-2100 by 10 days/year under a fully-adapting baseline (Fig. 3i, in pink), which also contributes to decreasing OAX-LOX event frequency under a shifting-mean baseline (Fig. 3f, in pink). Reduced H^+ - O_2 covariability is localized in parts of the high latitudes (Fig. 5i) and possibly explained by weaker vertical gradients in H^+ and O_2 at 2°C warming compared to 1890-1900 (Fig. S10), diminishing the contribution of isopycnal shifts to driving OAX-LOX events at 617m. In addition, changes
215 in T- H^+ covariability after 2050 slightly increase MHW-OAX event frequency under a fully-adapting baseline (Fig. 3g, in pink), thereby also raising MHW-OAX event frequency under a shifting-mean baseline (Fig. 3f, in pink).

When integrated over the entire ocean volume down to 2000m, the portion of ocean volume affected by an extreme or compound extreme event rapidly increases over 1891-2100 (Fig. 6). At "preindustrial" 1891-
220 1900 period, 20% of the ocean volume is affected by some type of extreme event at any given time on average over 1891-1900 (Fig. 6a, in grey). By 2000, 90% of the ocean volume is affected by an extreme event on average, when defining extremes relative to the preindustrial period. At 2°C global warming in year 2050, 98% of the ocean volume is affected, whereas by 2100, more than 99% of the ocean volume is affected by some type of extreme event. This strong increase in extreme event incidence is driven by an increase in
225 MHWs (in red+orange+purple+black), OAX events (in yellow+orange+green+black), and in LOX events (in blue+purple+green+black). The rapid increase in univariate OAX events from 1900 to 1975 (in yellow), slows down by 1975, as MHWs and LOX events increase as well and an increasing portion of the ocean volume is occupied by co-occurring OAX events with MHWs and/or LOX events. Triple compound MHW-OAX-LOX events, which occupied 1% of the ocean volume on average in the preindustrial period, occupy 9% by 2000, 30%

Figure 6: **Portion of the ocean volume occupied by an extreme or compound extreme event from 1891 to 2100, with extremes defined relative to a fixed preindustrial baseline or a baseline shifting over time to account for changes in the ocean’s mean state.** Portion of the ocean volume down to 2000m (%) occupied by no extreme event, by a univariate extreme event i.e. a marine heatwave (MHW, in red), a high acidity event (OAX, in yellow), or a low oxygen event (LOX, in blue), by a bivariate compound extreme event (MHW-OAX in orange, MHW-LOX in purple, or OAX-LOX in green), or by a triple compound event (MHW-OAX-LOX, in black), under (a) a fixed baseline or (b) a shifting-mean baseline in the GFDL-ESM2M large ensemble simulation.

230 by 2050 and almost 50% by 2100.

As discussed above, these strong increases in extreme event occurrence over the top 2000m of the ocean volume are mainly driven by long-term mean shift in T, $[H^+]$ and O_2 . Using a shifting-mean baseline, where percentile thresholds are shifted according to the long-term mean changes in T, $[H^+]$ and O_2 , the rise in extreme event occurrence is much smaller (Fig. 6b). The portion of the ocean volume occupied by an extreme event increases from 20% over the preindustrial period to 35% in 2100. Namely, $100-35=65\%$ of the ocean volume remains unaffected by an extreme event on average at any given time in 2100 when using a shifting-mean baseline (in grey, Fig. 6b), against less than 1% when using a fixed baseline. The rise in extreme event frequency under a shifting-mean baseline is mainly driven by an increase in univariate OAX events (in yellow, Fig. 6b).

Discussion and Conclusion

240 Our study shows that extreme conditions in temperature, acidity and oxygen frequently coincide at the sea surface, especially in the low to mid-latitudes, and that compound events also occur at subsurface depths. Between 200m and 1000m, MHWs frequently co-occur with OAX and LOX events, particularly in high latitude regions, whereas OAX-LOX events are widespread across the global ocean. The frequent occurrence of such compound events exposes marine species at various depths to co-occurring environmental stresses.

245 To improve our ability to predict potential impacts from compound events, it is essential to better understand

their drivers. This study investigates the potential role of vertical water mass displacements in driving subsurface compound events, although other processes, such as changes in biological activity, may also play an important role. In addition, there is a need to improve our understanding of the biological impacts of these events, not only on species inhabiting surface waters - such as those in coral reefs⁶⁵ and coastal and nearshore ecosystems⁶⁶ - but also on subsurface species, which are crucial for ecosystem functioning and provide key services to human societies. Pelagic species that move laterally and over the water column have been shown to escape adverse conditions by relocating or diving to deeper waters^{36,67,68,69}. Regions that remain relatively unaffected by compound events, such as the subtropical gyres of the Pacific around 617m, provide potential ecological refugia under climate change.

Our study is one of the very few addressing compound oceanic events at depth. Wong et al (2024) analysed subsurface compound events, yet over the historical period in a hindcast simulation spanning 1961-2020, using an alternative and complementary methodology⁴⁸. They define "column-compound events" as events when conditions are extreme for multiple ocean variables at the same time and in the same grid column, yet not necessarily at the same depth level. This "spatially-compounding" definition⁷⁰ is best suited to apprehend impacts on vertically-motile species, that dwell across the water column and can move up or down to escape univariate extreme events. Column-compound events restrict their habitable space, thereby potentially altering biotic interactions or enhancing predation and competition for food. The more classical "multivariate" definition⁷⁰, which we use in this study, is, in contrast, suited to analyse the drivers of co-occurring extreme conditions in multiple ocean variables, and to apprehend impacts on marine species that are vulnerable to extreme conditions in multiple variables yet less affected by univariate extreme events, which would not incite them to escape to deeper or shallower depths. These "column-compound" and "multivariate" definitions hence differ in their applications and biological relevance. Nevertheless, our study shares common results with Wong et al. (2024). Our study agrees, for example, on frequent MHW-OAX at the sea surface in the subtropics and throughout the water-column in the Southern Ocean, frequent OAX-LOX events in Eastern Boundary Upwelling Systems at 205m, and frequent MHW-LOX in the Bering Sea at 205m. Any comparison is however limited by our differing methodologies and by the fact that Wong et al.'s study⁴⁸ is restricted to the upper 300m and to the historical period, whereas we extend our analysis to 2000m and to the end of the 21st century. An alternative approach to these "multivariate" and "column-compound" definitions would be to consider compound events as events when conditions are simultaneously extreme for multiple variables at a certain grid cell in density coordinates, so as to exclude variability induced by isopycnal oscillations. Such approach would be well suited for marine species oscillating along with isopycnals, such as certain plankton species, but inadequate for species that are fixed at a certain depth or unaffected by isopycnal oscillations.

The definition of the baseline period is critical for the quantification of the long-term changes in univariate and compound extreme event occurrence (Smith et al. 2024 (Submitted),⁴²). With a fixed preindustrial baseline,

280 the annual mean portion of the upper ocean volume down to 2000m experiencing extreme events is projected to increase from 20% to over 99% between the preindustrial period and 2100 under a high emission scenario. In contrast, using a shifting-mean baseline limits this increase to 35%, underscoring the baseline’s critical role. The choice of baseline for defining marine heatwaves has been debated: Amaya et al. (2023)⁷¹ recommend a shifting-mean baseline, while Sen Gupta et al. (2023)⁷² prefer a fixed baseline, raising awareness of escalating
285 marine heatwave risks⁷³. Gruber et al. (2021)²⁴ and Li et al. (2023)⁷⁴ suggest using baselines relevant to ecosystem impacts. For studying compound events without particular biological impact considerations, we recommend using a combination of fixed, shifting-mean, and fully-adapting baselines to capture the influences of changes in the mean state, variability, and covariability on compound event dynamics under climate change.

A potential caveat of our study is that it relies on a single ESM, the GFDL-ESM2M. However, the
290 GFDL-ESM2M generally agrees with observation-based data for the present-day correlation across multiple ocean ecosystem stressors, except for subsurface events involving acidity possibly due to high uncertainties in observation-based $[H^+]$ estimates at these depths. In addition, the GFDL-ESM2M compares well with CMIP6 models, and its large ensemble simulation (LES) with daily-mean outputs down to 2000m enables a statistically-robust analysis, essential given the rarity of compound extreme events^{75,53}. Unlike single-member simulations
295 from multiple climate models, LES enable us to isolate natural climate variability from anthropogenic forced trends^{76,53} and to cleanly calculate the shifting-mean and fully-adapting baseline cases⁴².

Anthropogenic forced trends are, however, constrained over 2005-2100 by the choice of Representative Concentration Pathway. In this study, we analyzed output of the GFDL-ESM2M forced by RCP8.5. However, future research should also explore lower emission scenarios that align more closely with the target set by
300 the Paris Agreement. While future changes are expected to be smaller under these lower emissions scenarios, subsurface changes at 2°C global warming — as illustrated in Figures 4 and 5 — could be larger. This is because ocean warming, acidification, and deoxygenation would have more time to propagate to greater depths in slower-warming scenarios.

Another limitation is the GFDL-ESM2M’s relatively coarse resolution, which limits its ability to represent
305 mesoscale ocean and coastal processes, as well as fine-scale air–sea interactions^{77,78,24,79}. High-resolution models better capture marine heatwave characteristics in eddy-rich regions (e.g. western boundary currents, Southern Ocean) and represent low oxygen extremes in areas like the Eastern Pacific⁸⁰. However, resolution alone does not guarantee accurate simulations of low-oxygen zone dynamics and evolution. Additionally, the GFDL-ESM2M, as many other ESMs, lacks features such as ice-sheet ocean interactions, which limits its ability to represent
310 the future oceanic state in the high latitudes. Also, the GFDL-ESM2M has a simplified biogeochemical model, which hinders its accuracy in regions with high diurnal variability in seawater chemistry, especially in biologically active coastal areas⁸¹. To increase confidence in projections of surface and subsurface compound events under climate change, further studies are needed with high-resolution, biogeochemically enhanced ESMs, producing

LES with 3D high-temporal-resolution outputs.

315 Overall, this study provides first insights into the distribution and projected changes of ocean compound extreme events within the top 2000m. Our findings suggest that compound MHW-OAX, MHW-LOX, and OAX-LOX events are already common in certain surface and subsurface regions, yet are becoming increasingly frequent under climate change, thereby threatening marine ecosystems that are vulnerable to coinciding extreme conditions in T, $[H^+]$ and O_2 . Surface and subsurface compound events need to be closely observed and
320 mechanistically understood in order to predict their future occurrence and to moderate or prevent impacts on marine life.

Methods

GFDL-ESM2M large ensemble simulation

The GFDL-ESM2M is a fully coupled Earth system model developed at NOAA's Geophysical Fluid Dynamics
325 Laboratory (GFDL)^{56,57}. Its ocean circulation module, MOM4p1⁸², has 50 depth levels and a nominal 1° horizontal resolution which increases to $1/3^\circ$ near the equator. It is coupled to an ocean biogeochemistry module, TOPAZv2⁵⁷, which includes 30 tracers. TOPAZv2 describes the cycles of carbon, oxygen, alkalinity, nutrients, lithogenic material and surface sediment calcite, as well as their interaction with three phytoplankton groups and heterotrophic biomass. Zooplankton grazing is implicitly simulated. All routines for ocean carbonate
330 chemistry follow the OCMIP2 protocol⁸³. At well oxygenated conditions, unprotected organic matter fraction is remineralized with a constant depth scale of 188 m. Remineralization is slower at low O_2 and suppressed in the absence of O_2 ($<1 \mu\text{mol kg}^{-1}$). The remineralization and sinking speed of organic material is insensitive to temperature.

We used a large ensemble simulation (LES) of the GFDL-ESM2M, which consists of 15 ensemble members
335 under the same external forcing, but each starting from slightly different initial conditions⁴². An ensemble of 15 members was generated by perturbing the temperature on the 1st of January 1861 by the order of $10^{-5} \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ for 5 ensemble members at a grid cell at the surface of the Weddell Sea, for 5 members at the surface of the North Atlantic, and for 5 members in the deep North Pacific^{42,43}. These 15 simulations were forced with prescribed historical concentrations of atmospheric CO_2 and non- CO_2 radiative-forcing agents from 1861 to 2005, and then
340 by a high-emission no-mitigation scenario (RCP8.5; RCP: Representative Concentration Pathway) from 2006 to 2100⁸⁴. The global atmospheric surface temperature is projected to rise by $3.69 \pm 0.45 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ from preindustrial period to 2081-2100. We corrected for a residual model drift by first computing the linear trend of temperature, $[H^+]$ and O_2 in a 1000-yr long control simulation at each grid cell and then removing these trends in the 15-member LES.

345 We focus on the 1891-2100 time period, and consider 1891-1900 as our "preindustrial" period. This prein-

dustrial time period is sufficiently long to analyze compound extreme events using the 15 ensemble members. Additionally, it starts late enough - 8 years after the Krakatoa eruption - for the volcanic climate signal to have largely subsided in the ocean's mixed layer⁸⁵ while also allowing sufficient time for the memory of the initial conditions to fade⁸⁶.

350 Definition of extreme and compound extreme events

We define extreme events as days when an ocean variable is outside the norm relative to its climatological variability. Specifically, marine heatwaves (MHW) are days when temperature exceeds the local seasonally-varying 90th percentile of temperature, high acidity events (OAX) days when $[H^+]$ exceeds its 90th percentile, and low oxygen events (LOX) days when O_2 is lower than its 10th percentile. The respective percentile thresholds
355 are calculated at each grid cell and for each calendar day over the period selected as climatological baseline, and across the entire LES. This local, seasonally-varying extreme event definition implies homogeneous frequency over the global ocean and throughout the year over the baseline period. For instance, when MHW, OAX and LOX events are defined based on the preindustrial 1891-1900 baseline, their mean frequency over 1891-1900 is 10% (or 36.5 days/years) at each grid cell and on each calendar day.

360 Multivariate compound extreme events occur when extreme conditions coincide for multiple ocean variables at an individual grid cell and at the same day. Under the assumption of independence between univariate events, compound MHW-OAX events, compound MHW-LOX events, and compound OAX-LOX events would occur with a frequency of $10\% * 10\% = 1\%$ (or 3.65 days/years) on average over the baseline period. The likelihood multiplication factor (LMF) is a metric commonly used in compound event studies to describe how
365 many times more or less likely compound events are compared to their expected frequency under the assumption of independence^{87,37}. In our study, the LMF for compound MHW-OAX events is defined as:

$$\text{LMF}(\text{MHW-OAX}) = \frac{f(\text{MHW-OAX})}{f(\text{MHW}) * f(\text{OAX})} = \frac{f(\text{MHW-OAX}) (\%)}{10\% * 10\%} = \frac{f(\text{MHW-OAX})}{1\%} \quad (1)$$

An LMF of 2 for example means that MHW-OAX events occur twice as often as would be expected if MHW and OAX events were independent. The LMF of MHW-LOX events and OAX-LOX events is defined in a similar
370 way.

In the "Present-day distribution" section, we define extreme and compound extreme events based on the 2004-2019 baseline period over which observations are available. For simplicity, we decided not to detrend time series of T, $[H^+]$ and O_2 prior to identifying extreme and compound extreme events. Note that linearly detrending does not qualitatively alter compound event frequency patterns (not shown).

375 In the "Historical and future changes" section, we assess historical and future changes in compound extreme event frequency with respect to (i) a fixed preindustrial baseline, (ii) a shifting-mean baseline, and (iii) a

fully-adapting baseline⁴². Under a fixed baseline, percentile thresholds are calculated over the preindustrial 1891-1900 period across the entire LES. Under a shifting-mean baseline, these thresholds are shifted over time to remove long-term changes in the ocean’s mean state over 1891-2100. We use as percentile thresholds the
380 ones calculated over 1891-1900, to which we added the ensemble mean changes in T, H⁺ and O₂, smoothed using a 365-day running mean filter to remove the seasonal cycle. Lastly, under a fully-adapting baseline, we use percentile thresholds which accommodate changes in the ocean’s mean state and variability. To do so, we first detrended the T, H⁺, and O₂ time series of each ensemble member by removing for each variable the associated 365-day smoothed ensemble mean. We then recalculated the percentile thresholds over successive
385 25-year detrended periods (1901-1925, 1926-1950, [...] 2076-2100), and smoothed them using a 30-year running mean for each calendar day to prevent jumps between successive 25-year periods. The reason why we did not directly calculate the percentile thresholds over moving 30-year periods is to reduce computational demands. Both methods would yield similar results⁴². Under a fully-adapting baseline, MHW, OAX, and LOX event frequencies remain mostly constant (around 10% or 36.5 days/year) across the time series, and any change in
390 compound event frequency can only be driven by a change in covariability between ocean variables.

Isopycnal displacements during compound extreme events

In the "Potential drivers of subsurface compound events" section, we link compound event frequency patterns at subsurface in the GFDL-ESM2M-LE to isopycnal displacements during compound events, indicated by density anomalies relative to the seasonal cycle. A positive anomaly of the potential density referenced to 0
395 dbar indicates an isopycnal heaving, whereas a negative anomaly indicates an isopycnal deepening. Density anomalies are averaged during compound events defined at monthly resolution to match the monthly resolution of the potential density output.

Observation-based data

We evaluate the GFDL-ESM2M’s ability to represent correlations across T, [H⁺], and O₂ against observations
400 over 2004-2019, the period over which observation-based T, [H⁺] and O₂ are available at monthly resolution down to 1500 m depth. For surface T, we use NOAA’s satellite-based daily high-resolution Optimum Interpolation SST (OISST) analysis product with a horizontal resolution of 0.25°^{88,89}. For subsurface T as well as for surface and subsurface O₂, we use the GOBAI-O₂ data product⁵⁵, which is based on in-situ data collected by Argo floats. GOBAI-O₂ algorithms are trained on sparse in-situ O₂ data to derive a global O₂ product from T and
405 salinity fields constructed from Argo float measurements. The dataset covers 86% of the global ocean area with a 1° horizontal resolution for 59 vertical levels, from 2004 to 2021 at monthly resolution. [H⁺] at sea surface is provided by Burger et al. 2022⁴², who reconstructed 1982-2019 [H⁺] at monthly resolution in two steps, by first deriving total alkalinity (TA) from EN4.2.1 SST and salinity fields⁹⁰ using the LIARv2 algorithm⁹¹, and then

deriving $[H^+]$ at a 1° horizontal grid resolution using the CO₂SYS carbonate chemistry python package⁹² from
410 surface salinity, SST, TA and from the interpolated global surface pCO₂ product MPI-SOMFNN⁹³. Similarly,
we calculated $[H^+]$ below the sea surface in two steps. We first derived TA from GOBAl-O₂ T, O₂, and salinity
fields using the LIARv2 algorithm. We then used the CO₂SYS package to derive $[H^+]$ as a function of T, S,
TA, climatological mean phosphate and silicate concentrations from the World Ocean Atlas down to 800m⁹⁴
and from the GFDL-ESM2M-LE averaged over 2004-2019 from 800m to 1500m, as well as dissolved inorganic
415 carbon (DIC) from the Mapped Observation-Based Oceanic DIC dataset (MOBO-DIC,⁵⁴). MOBO-DIC is an
estimate of DIC based on ship observations and interpolated by machine learning.

The monthly-mean observation-based T, $[H^+]$, and O₂ products were regridded to a 1° horizontal grid.
Their vertical levels were linearly interpolated to match MOBO-DIC's 28 levels from the surface to 1500 m
depth. We extracted monthly-mean T, $[H^+]$, and O₂ time series over the period ranging from 2004 to 2019 over
420 which MOBO-DIC is available. Given that this period is too short for a statistically-robust analysis of rare
compound extreme event at monthly resolution, we did not compare the frequency of compound extreme event
in the GFDL-ESM2M-LE and in the observations. Instead, we compared the Pearson correlation coefficient
between monthly-mean de-seasonalized anomalies of each pair of two ocean variables in the GFDL-ESM2M-LE
and in the observations. The frequency of a certain compound event mainly reflects the correlation between its
425 associated variables⁸⁷. For instance, in the GFDL-ESM2M-LE, the MHW-OAX event frequency (Fig. 1) is high
where T and $[H^+]$ are positively correlated and low where they are negatively correlated (Fig. S2). In addition,
compound event frequencies in the GFDL-ESM2M-LE follow the same spatial pattern when computed at daily
or at monthly resolution ($r > 0.98$ for each pair of extreme events and at any depth level). We can therefore expect
the model to correctly represent the present-day distribution of compound extreme events at daily resolution
430 over regions where it agrees with observation-based products on the correlation between monthly-mean ocean
anomalies. Before comparing correlations, we linearly interpolated the vertical levels of the GFDL-ESM2M-LE
correlation estimates to match the depth levels of the observation-based estimates.

CMIP6 model data

We also compute the correlation between ocean variables in simulations obtained from Earth system models that
435 participated in the sixth phase of the Coupled Model Intercomparison Project (CMIP6) under the historical
period over 1850-2014 and the SSP585 scenario over 2015-2100⁹⁵. Following Earth system models provided
the necessary output data: Can-ESM5⁹⁶, CNRM-ESM2-1⁹⁷, GFDL-CM4⁹⁸, GFDL-ESM4⁹⁹, IPSL-CM6A¹⁰⁰,
MPI-ESM1-2¹⁰¹, MRI-ESM2¹⁰², NorESM2¹⁰³, and UKESM1-0¹⁰⁴. $[H^+]$ was missing for Can-ESM5 and MRI-
ESM2 (table 1). All model data are regridded to a 1° horizontal grid, vertically interpolated to match the 28
440 depth levels of MOBO-DIC, and extracted over the period ranging from 2004 to 2019 at monthly resolution.

	CanESM5	CNRM-ESM2-1	GFDL-CM4	GFDL-ESM4	IPSL-CM6A	MPI-ESM1-2	MRI-ESM2	NorESM2	UKESM1-0
T	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓
[H ⁺]		✓	✓	✓	✓	✓		✓	✓
O ₂	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓

Table 1: CMIP6 model data available at monthly resolution over 2004-2019 for temperature (T), H⁺ concentration ([H⁺]), and dissolved oxygen concentration (O₂)

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Author contribution

NLG and TLF designed the study. TLF and FAB provided the GFDL-ESM2M output. FAB provided the
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NLG performed the analysis and wrote the initial draft of the manuscript. All authors discussed the analysis
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Competing Interests

The authors declare that they have no competing financial interests.

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